

Agreement between Canada and Newfoundland on Rare Diseases

Issue/Problem

On November 15, 2024, the governments of Canada and of Newfoundland signed the National strategy for Drugs for Rare Disease Agreement (DRD) to support enhanced access to early diagnosis, screening for rare diseases, and improved access to existing and new drugs for rare diseases. This strategy requires an investment of \$22 million over three years.

Description of the problem

Approximately one million Canadians are affected by rare diseases. These diseases often appear at birth or emerge in early childhood. For 94% of these conditions, there is no treatment available. Although Canadians with rare diseases need access to drugs, as of 2019, there were 93 drugs for rare diseases approved in Canada that cost over \$100,000 per patient per year, over half of which cost more than \$200,000.

Results

This agreement is part of the first phase of Canada's National Strategy for Drugs for rare disease which includes an investment of \$1.5 billion by the Canadian government and \$1.4 billion by the provinces and territories over three years to help patients with rare disease achieve a better quality of life and access treatments as early as possible. This project includes work with provinces and territories individually as well as by pan-Canadian partners who are key stakeholders in the drug development pipeline. The strategy further includes a plan to create a short common list of new drugs to be cost-shared across the country after negotiations with the pan-Canadian Pharmaceutical Alliance. Newfoundland and Labrador will designate an official or official(s) for the duration of this Agreement to represent its interests related to performance measurement. This includes supporting, through committee structures as they

Policy Brief

Together,
there's
something
science
can do.

may be established, the establishment and strengthening of national governance and data infrastructure for DRD.

Lessons Learned

The impact of this agreement on public health and access to pharmaceuticals remains difficult to assess. Strong performance measurement and reporting standards, as well as conditions for the annual renewal of federal funding under the agreement, provide a basis for cautious optimism for the success of the strategy.

Source:

<https://www.canada.ca/en/health-canada/news/2024/11/backgrounder-drugs-for-rare-diseases--newfoundland-and-labrador-agreement.html>

<https://www.canada.ca/en/health-canada/corporate/transparency/health-agreements/shared-health-priorities/drugs-for-rare-diseases-bilateral-agreements/newfoundland-labrador.html#a6>

<https://www.ourcommons.ca/Content/Committee/421/HESA/Reports/RP10349306/hesarp22/hesarp22-e.pdf>

<https://www.canada.ca/en/health-canada/programs/consultation-national-strategy-high-cost-drugs-rare-diseases-online-engagement/what-we-heard.html>